

PEDAGOGICAL TECHNIQUE AS AN INTEGRAL PART OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILL.**Abdullazhonova Shakhnoza Akbarovna**

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Abstract. *The article considers pedagogical technique as a set of skills that allow the teacher to see, hear and feel his pupils, each teacher must master the pedagogical technique, know its components that ensure the success of his work. Also in the article we will talk about such components of pedagogical technology: the culture of speech, the ability to dress, the ability to master gestures and facial expressions, the ability to control your body.*

Key words: *pedagogical technique, components of pedagogical technique, culture of speech, diction, gesture, facial expressions.*

**ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ТЕХНИКА КАК НЕОТЪЕМЛЕМАЯ ЧАСТЬ
ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОГО МАСТЕРСТВА.**

Аннотация. *В статье педагогическая техника рассматривается как совокупность умений, которые позволяют учителю видеть, слышать и чувствовать своих учеников, каждый педагог должен владеть педагогической техникой, знать ее составляющие, обеспечивающие успех его работы. Также в статье мы поговорим о таких компонентах педагогической технологии: культура речи, умение одеваться, умение владеть жестами и мимикой, умение владеть своим телом.*

Ключевые слова: *педагогическая техника, компоненты педагогической техники, культура речи, дикция, жест, мимика.*

**“The teacher must be able to organize, walk, joke, be cheerful, angry... behave in
such a way that every movement educates him.”**

A.S. Makarenko.

The profession of a teacher is not only a profession, it is a calling. What do you need to have to become a teacher? First of all, he must be a wise, knowledgeable mentor and an artist at the same time.

Pedagogical technique is an integral part of pedagogical skill. The most important part of teaching skills is professional knowledge and skills. The most important components of the foundations of pedagogical mastery are the professional knowledge of the teacher, his professional

- humanistic orientation, pedagogical abilities and pedagogical techniques. The term “pedagogical technique” was introduced by A. S. Makarenko. He viewed her as the core of education.

Pedagogical skill is determined by three interrelated parts: pedagogical theory, pedagogical technique and method of working on the material of the lesson topic, its organization and conduct.

But if it is enough to study the theory, then pedagogical technique and skill must be mastered, i.e. You need to develop certain teaching skills. This is achieved through long-term and systematic training, when pedagogical techniques are brought to the level of subconscious, reflexive activity. The task of a pedagogical educational institution is not only to accustom the student to daily work on himself, but also to instill in him the need to improve his skills throughout his entire teaching work. The educational process at school is a complex, multifaceted, dynamic phenomenon. It has long been known that pedagogical action is akin to art. It is also known that art is born from the fusion of talent and skill. Professional excellence is achieved through the constant work of a talented teacher on himself. The teacher is a creator. His creativity is expressed in the flow of living human speech and living human movements, in a direct emotional impact on students. This is the secret of the extraordinary influence of the best teachers on their students.

Pedagogical technique promotes the harmonious unity of the internal content of the teacher’s activity and its external expression. The skill of a teacher lies in the synthesis of spiritual culture and pedagogically appropriate external expressiveness.

Thus, technology is a set of techniques. Its means are speech and non-verbal means of communication.

The pedagogical process requires a kind of “magic” of pedagogical influence. To create it, you need to be fluent in the technique of interpersonal communication. Anyone who wants to penetrate the secrets of self-ownership.

Y. P. Azarov argued that, firstly, developed pedagogical technology helps the teacher to express himself more deeply and brightly in teaching activities, to reveal in interaction with students all the best, professionally significant in his personality. Secondly, pedagogical technology also has a developmental impact on personality traits. The peculiarity of pedagogical techniques is that they all have a pronounced individual-personal character, i.e. are formed on the basis of the individual psychophysiological characteristics of the teacher. Thirdly, in the process of mastering pedagogical techniques, the moral and aesthetic positions of the teacher are most fully revealed.

Pedagogical technology consists of two components - internal and external.

Internal technique is the psychological attitude of the teacher for the upcoming activity with the help of mind, will and feelings.

External technique is the manifestation of the teacher's internal experiences in his facial expressions, voice, language and movements.

Speaking about internal technology, first of all, we mean the ability of a teacher to develop qualities that give him the opportunity to carry out his professional activities without unnecessary stress. These qualities include:

- pedagogical optimism;
- self-confidence as a teacher;
- ability to control oneself;
- presence of strong-willed qualities (self-control, focus, etc.)

Elements of the teacher's external technique are verbal (linguistic, speech) and non-verbal means.

There is a wide range of non-verbal communication methods. Among them, not unimportant are: the appearance of the teacher, since it should evoke a positive attitude of the student towards the teacher; pantomime, i.e. expressive movements of the whole body or its individual parts; manner of standing correctly in front of students; ability to maintain social distance; facial expressions and eye contact. An integral part of a teacher's skill is his speech. A significant contribution to the development of both pedagogical skills and pedagogical technology itself was made by scientist-teachers Yu.P. Azarov, V. A. Mudrik, M. M. Yakovlev and others.

What is the essence of pedagogical technology, what components are included in it? For the first time, components of pedagogical technology were implemented by A. S. Makarenko. Summarizing his experience and the experience of other teachers, V. N. Grineva identifies the following components of pedagogical technique:

1. The ability to dress and take care of your appearance.
2. Speech culture: focus, logical literacy, pace and rhythm, intonation, diction, breathing.
3. The ability to control your body.
4. Ability to master gestures and facial expressions.
5. Psychotechnical skills: understanding your mental state, the ability to control it, the ability to choose the pace and rhythm of your work.
6. Pedagogical communication skills.

Speech culture is speech mastery, the ability to choose a stylistically appropriate option, expressively and intelligibly express a thought. The teacher must pronounce words correctly, place emphasis correctly, etc. Speech is a powerful means of personality formation. The quality of speech is reduced by tautology - repetition of the same thing in different words: "running", "playing a game", etc.

Intonation is of great importance for oral speech, which comes in two types: logical and emotionally expressive. The purpose of the first is to emphasize the meaning of individual words and expressions, the second is to help the teacher convey his feelings and attitude to what was said.

I would especially like to emphasize the harm of “parasite words” (well, so to speak, as they say, etc.), clogging speech. All this complicates the perception of information.

Diction is the clarity and correctness of pronunciation of individual sounds, which are ensured by the correct functioning of the speech organs. The articulatory apparatus must work actively, without unnecessary tension. All sounds and their combinations must be pronounced clearly, easily and freely at any tempo.

A gesture is a movement of the hands that accompanies the teacher’s speech, enhances its expressiveness, and sometimes replaces it. Gestures reveal a person's mental state. When using gestures, you need to remember that they are natural, appropriate, restrained, i.e. corresponded to the specific pedagogical situation. There are three groups of gestures: mechanical, descriptive and psychological. It should be remembered that excessive gestures distract from the main thing and can be funny.

Facial expressions are a means of conveying one’s feelings, emotions, and attitude towards something using the muscles of the face. To prevent facial expressions from becoming antics, they must correspond to the mental state of the teacher. What feelings can a teacher convey using facial expressions? These are grief, anger, joy, embarrassment, surprise, etc. Unlike gestures, which can be traditional in a certain situation, facial expressions are purely individual and depend, first of all, on the individual characteristics of the teacher.

The method of formation of pedagogical technology includes:

1. A system of training exercises to develop certain skills;
2. A system of certain rules and requirements for future professional activities.

Thus, every teacher must master pedagogical techniques and know its components that ensure the success of his activities.

A diversified teacher evokes the admiration and pride of his students. They want to imitate him, they want to learn more. A teacher must have an arsenal of means by which he conveys his experience and his visions. The teacher not only organizes the work of the children's team as a whole, but also forms the personal relationships of children among themselves, in communication with adults, and in general with the world around them.

And in conclusion, let us cite the words of A. S. Makarenko, “The skill of a teacher is not some special art... but it is a specialty that must be taught, just like a doctor should be taught his skill, how a musician should be taught.”

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